

ENCOURAGE CHILDREN IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES!

Yulduzxon Raximova Abduraxmon qizi

Farg'ona viloyati Rishton tumani

7-umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktabi

Ingliz tili fani o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: chet tillarini o'rganishning ahamiyati, til o'rganishda o'qituvchi va ota-onaning roli, rag'batlantirish yo'llari.

Kalit so'zlar: rag'batlantirish, ingliz tili muhiti, ruhlantiruvchi iboralar, chet tillarini o'rganish.

Annotation: importance of learning foreign languages, the role of teachers and parents in learning language.

Key words: encouragement, English environment, expressions for motivation, learning language.

Аннотация: важность изучения иностранных языков, роль учителей и родителей в изучении языка.

Ключевые слова: поощрение, английская среда, выражения для мотивации, изучение языка.

In our developing country, it is pivotal to learn another language for child's future life. Principally, the government is taking into consideration to learn English language widely. Namely, as Flora Lewis said: „learning another language is not only learning different words for the same things, but learning another way to think about things”.

Thus, I am going to appeal both teachers and parents in the consequence of having responsibility for the child's education. Particularly, it is clear that the better the child study, the better he may live in the future. Therefore, I want to recommend parents and teachers some useful tips of motivating and training children to learn foreign languages.

Entirely, the child who is younger can easily get accustomed to English. First of all, parents should create chances and condition for their children to study foreign languages at first grades before their teenage years. Because, children are more interested in being around English environment. In this way, you can use several colorful pictures, funny words in English in order to decorate their rooms.

Secondly, that is essential guidance to study English with parents for children at home. So as your child can feel confident and be interested in learning you should help with your attempt and encouragement. At this moment, you can train together, fill your child's world with reading, read them short stories.

Thirdly, if teachers also use some enjoyable methods like movies, games, songs, computers and presentations in teaching English that will improve child's interest and knowledge. At the same time, parents should find entertainment in learning languages, in order to acquire perfect education. For instance, you play games with using English words or grammar rules and vocabulary, sing songs with lyrics as well. You can learn yourself too. It is of great importance that provide with enjoyment for your child.

In addition, I can recommend that rewarding the child all the time is vital route of learning English well. Therefore, teachers also should pay attention to child's knowledge and his emotional statement. There are times when you meet someone in a happy or sad situation and you want to encourage them. But most children tend to be depressed according to teacher's feedback. When if your

pupils make a mistake or good effort but fail, you should grasp and explain in positive way not using punishment. In that position, you can use several ways of feedback, like „Don't give up”, „Hang in there”, „Stay strong”, „Good effort”, „You can do it”. In the contrast, if the pupil has done something good, you can say „Good job”, „Well done”, „You did great”, „I'm proud of you”!

As a conclusion, I can say that we, teachers always act in the sphere encouragement in teaching foreign languages. Namely, teachers who love teaching, teach children to love learning. Moreover, motivate the child in order that it has confidence in one same. But it is necessary to have patience with every child because all it does not have the same evolutionary development.

Used literature:

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